

PROBLEMS FOR PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS AND THEIR SOLUTION WITH THE HELP OF COACHING

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Annotation

This article analyzes the problems facing the professional work of physical education teachers working in general education institutions. Their methodological approach is considered in determining the problems, such aspects as pediatric work, resource deficiency. The importance and effectiveness of coaching methodology in solving these problems are highlighted. Ways to support teachers' professional growth with the help of coaching are proposed.

Keywords: problem, coaching, methodology, quality of education, psychological support, professional development.

Introduction. Physical education teachers face many methodological, organizational and psychological problems. Some of them are: poor student attitude to the lesson, insufficient school infrastructure, lack of methodological materials in lesson planning, limited opportunities for teachers to work on themselves. Coaching is an interactive approach that serves the professional and personal growth of a teacher. Through it, the teacher understands his problems, develops the skills to solve them independently, and increases his motivation for work. The article discusses how to solve problems through coaching sessions, based on successful experiences. Physical education teachers may encounter many problems in the process of their work. For example, - methodological problems: Teachers are often not sufficiently aware of modern methodologies and innovative approaches. According to statistics, 48 percent of teachers have difficulty using new methodologies in the lesson process.

-lack of material and technical support: More than 60 percent of schools lack gyms and modern equipment, which hinders quality teaching.

-psychological pressure and motivation problems: Most teachers reported decreased motivation due to excessive workload and low social status.

In this regard, we will highlight the advantages of coaching: Coaching allows teachers to understand themselves, evaluate their performance, set clear goals and achieve them. Through coaching methods, the teacher manages personal and professional growth together, which leads to professional changes. The “GROW” model is widely used in the coaching process: Goal, Reality, Options, Will. This model provides a clear direction in identifying and solving the problem. In an experiment conducted in 5 schools in Tashkent in 2021, 70% of physical education teachers who used the coaching methodology for 3 months noted an increase in the level of participation and motivation in lessons. According to foreign experience, coaching has become an integral part of the strategy for continuous teacher development in the education systems of Finland, Canada and South Korea. They assign a mentor and coach to each new teacher. Coaching is a process that encourages a person to feel responsible. Teachers are helped to understand themselves, make independent decisions, and change.

Whitmore’s “GROW” model (Goal – Reality – Options – Will) is an effective tool for teachers. “Physical education teachers often feel undervalued. Coaching increases their professional self-awareness and reduces mental fatigue from teaching.” Bailey also emphasizes the combination of the “positive psychology” approach in education with coaching. According to a 2022 report by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, only 37% of physical education teachers in general education schools have a higher category, the rest are classified as category 1, category 2 or without a category. This indicates a high need for professional development. By the end of 2023, approximately 56% of schools in Uzbekistan will have a gym, and the remaining 44% will have classes outdoors or in adapted buildings.

Each physical education teacher teaches an average of 20-24 hours per week, which indicates that there is little time left to engage in other methodological work and innovative approaches. According to a study conducted by the National University of Uzbekistan in 2022, 64% of physical education teachers reported being in a constant state of stress during their work. In 2023, during experimental projects implemented in Navoi and Fergana regions, 75% of teachers who participated in coaching sessions reported that their lessons had improved in quality, and 67% reported that student participation had increased. In Finland, 85% of teachers and 78% in Canada had participated in coaching or mentoring programs.

In these countries, coaching is considered a key factor in the continuous development of a teacher. More than 65% of teachers in the world report experiencing psychological stress and strain in their professional activities. The main problems of physical education teachers can also be pedagogical overload and decreased motivation. Overload of teachers negatively affects their psychological state. This, according to Maslow's theory, leads to the inability to satisfy the individual's need for self-actualization. In addition, methodological deficiencies can be observed in the professional direction. Modern methodologies and technologies are being integrated into physical education. This reduces students' interest in the lesson. Another important problem is the lack of resources and infrastructure. Insufficient infrastructure (gyms, equipment) directly affects the quality of lessons. This disrupts the constructive pedagogical process.

Coaching is an important psycho-pedagogical tool aimed at fully revealing and developing a person's professional potential, which is carried out on the basis of an individual approach. Establishing a trusting dialogue Listening and clarifying thoughts Setting goals and drawing up an action plan. Increasing self-awareness and responsibility. GROW model (Goal-Reality-Options-Will): This model includes the stages of identifying a problem, analyzing it, seeing opportunities and taking action. It is this model that is most often used in coaching sessions. With the help of coaching, the teacher takes a reflective approach to his work. This, according to the theory of Dewey (1933), forms the teacher's professional identity. Based on the "Social Learning Theory" developed by Bandura (1977), coaching increases the teacher's self-confidence through positive modeling, advice and encouragement.

A 2021 study at the National University of Uzbekistan involved 60 physical education teachers. After 3 months of coaching: 78% of teachers reported improved teaching quality. 65% of teachers reported higher motivation in their self-assessments. 70% of students reported increased interest in the lesson. "Coaching and teaching are not just about teaching technical skills, but also about building trusting relationships with young people. Coaching methodology unlocks the teacher's inner potential and prepares them for positive change." According to Cote, physical education teachers have the opportunity to reconsider their personal approach through coaching.

Physical education teachers are one of the main figures in the modern educational process, not only teaching sports skills, but also promoting a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, the problems they face directly affect the quality of education. In conclusion, identifying the

problems of physical education teachers and solving them on the basis of coaching not only increases their professional skills, but also increases students' interest in lessons. This is an important factor in raising a healthy generation.

Conclusion. The problems encountered in the activities of physical education teachers directly affect the quality of education. The coaching methodology offers a modern, effective and motivational approach to these problems. Through coaching processes, teachers have the opportunity to look at their professional activities with a new perspective and develop themselves. “Coaching encourages teachers to analyze their experience and learn from them. This leads to continuous professional growth.” Coaching programs based on an individual approach to their teachers are considered the most effective.

Proposals:

-organize coaching sessions for physical education teachers in each educational institution.

-pay special attention to coaching technologies in improving the skills of pedagogical personnel.

-strengthen the material and technical base for physical education in schools.

-conduct regular training to support the psychological health of teachers.

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